

Influence of operating parameters on process behavior and product quality in fertilizer manufacturing using continuous hopper transfer pan granulation

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Abstract

The present work investigates continuous pan granulation using dolomite primary particles and sprayed solution of sodium lignosulphonate binder. Individual changes of operating parameters were investigated with respect to their influences on process behavior and product quality. The latter is characterized in terms of the granules' characteristic size, compressive strength, angle of repose, bulk density, and humidity. The experimental results show clear trends between operation parameters and product granules' characteristic properties. It is shown that all investigated operation parameters have a significant effect on the particle size distribution and the average diameter of the granules: the average particle size increases with increasing binder flow rate to feed rate ratio, increasing binder concentration and inclination angle of the pan. For the angle of repose and the bulk density the ratio of binder flow rate to raw material flow rate and humidity is shown to be the most significant influence factor.

1 Introduction

Fertilizers, plant protection products and soil conditioners of natural origin are increasingly used in both conventional and organic agriculture. The widespread and often excessive use of fertilizers results in progressive soil acidification and consequently reduces the yield and quality of crop production. Acid rains additionally contribute to soil degradation. Under these circumstances, the use of commercially available magnesium-calcium fertilizers for deacidification purposes is no longer sufficient, and enrichment with suitable trace elements is required. One of such fertilizers is dolomite, which in powder form, after grinding, acts as a fertilizer providing magnesium and calcium to the soil [1–3]. It improves the quality of soil, especially acidic soil, and features good plant availability. The disadvantage of dolomite in powder form is the difficulty of its application. The unavoidable presence of a certain amount of dust in the mass (bed) of ground dolomite results in unintentional dispersion into the surrounding area during spreading, or any other form of soil application, which may in some cases cause specific environmental damage. An effective remedy to prevent unanticipated dusting of dolomite is granulation [1,2,4].

The most common focus of that process is size enlargement, i.e. fusion of fine powder particles to larger agglomerates. Furthermore, other properties like particle shape and mechanical strength are of interest, which have direct impact on product properties, like flowability and dusting tendency [5–12].

A wide range of granulation devices are commonly found in industrial application, including: fluidized-beds, drums, extruders and discs [8,13]. For fertilizer manufacturing, the granulation of dusty raw materials is commonly carried out by hopper mixing in pan granulators because of the technical simplicity and economic advantages of the process [9,10,14–16]. Here, granulated forms provide uniform composition allowing uniform supply of macro and microelements to the soil and reduction of the tendency for fertilizer aging, e.g., the tendency for phosphorus to volatilize into forms not available to plants. The biggest disadvantage of the fertilizer granulation process is increase in the cost of their manufacture, which can reach 30%. The continuous operation mode is especially promising with that respect as it enables constant throughput and product quality in terms of desired granule properties compared to batch operation [17].

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of formation of agglomerates.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of pan granulation process.

In the continuous pan transfer granulator, depicted schematically in Fig. 2, the particles of powder material are set in circular motion on the rotating pan of the device. During the granulation process, a binding liquid (binder) is distributed, e.g., by spraying, onto the material. As a result of wetting and continually repeated contact and separation, the granulated material builds up. Initially, agglomerates of small size and loose structure are formed. These agglomerates form the nucleus of the granules themselves. In the course of time, the seed particles are repeatedly covered by successive layers of moistened material particles during the pan circular motion. This leads to a gradual increase in the size of the granules until they reach the desired size and mechanical properties [18,19]. An additional advantageous and representative feature of pan granulation is the simultaneous classification of the granular material in terms of size, i.e., separation of its components caused by the difference in their size and density [20,21]. In the case of pan granulators, it is called trajectory segregation, where larger particles (with higher kinetic energy) travel further than smaller ones. As a result of this type of segregation, granules with smaller mass, and therefore smaller dimensions, move along tracks with smaller radius (closer to the axis of the machine), while larger granules, which are affected by a higher centrifugal force, are thrown towards the circumference of the granulator.

Due to the occurrence of the so-called trajectory segregation, an intermediate product, termed as pan sample, is formed. The pan sample is acquired directly from the granulator pan. Larger granules, which are subjected to greater centrifugal force, are thrown outside, and form the granulation product. In order to fully analyze the effect of operating parameters on the pan granulation process, it is therefore

necessary to determine the effect of changes in process parameters on the difference between properties of the pan and product samples.

An efficient and economical operation of granulation requires the use of suitable binders, i.e., agents that bind solid phase particles into agglomerates. They are usually solid substances with a strongly developed surface which makes them to have a high surface energy [22]. Lignin binders, containing sodium and calcium lignosulfonates are widely applied to make full utilization of the properties of dolomite in soil. Calcium lignosulfonate was proved to provide the best granulation conditions for dolomite granulation while sodium lignosulfonate for limestone meal [23–25].

In general, the mechanical strength of the wet granulation product, which is a crucial parameter for the fertilizer in practice, depends on at least three types of forces: intergrain friction, surface tension and capillary forces associated with the presence of liquids, which are predominant in static systems, and viscous forces associated with the presence of liquids, mainly active in dynamic systems [26]. In a number of experimental studies, attempts have been made to determine the influence of individual physicochemical parameters and process conditions on the granulate properties [11,13,27–31], including: angle of repose, bulk density, compressive strength and humidity. Angle of repose determines material flowability, which is important property influencing on processing, storage, and conveying particular materials [32]. Materials with low angle of repose are highly flowable and can be transported using gravitational force or a little energy [33]. Physically, the angle of repose can be defined as the angle that differentiates the transitions between phases of the granular material [34]. It is the steepest slope of the unconfined material and was measured from the horizontal plane on which the material can be heaped without collapsing [35]. Bulk density is of importance for economical and functional reasons. High bulk density is desirable for reducing shipping and packaging costs. On the other hand, low bulk density, influences other properties, such as flowability [36]. Another important parameter of granules is the compressive strength [12,37–39]. It is an indicator of the ability to resist the external forces acting on the granules and one of the most important criteria for evaluating fertilizer quality. A generally accepted measure of the compressive strength is the force required to crush the granule.

Humidity is a very important property for the formation of new and durable agglomerates. Humidity of the granules affects their dynamic mechanical strength and product durability [27].

The literature items discussed above refer to the properties of the granulation product. There is a lack of references to the properties of the intermediate product in the granulator pan formed during continuous granulation. The properties of the intermediate product taken from the granulator pan and the influence of operating parameters on these properties are crucial to achieve granules with appropriate properties. Therefore, in this work, attempts are made to evaluate the effect of operation parameters, such as: binder

flow rate, powder feed rate, binder content in water solution, rotation speed of the pan and inclination angle of the pan on particle size distribution (PSD), angle of repose, bulk density, humidity and the compressive strength, of both final and intermediate products in a lab-scale continuous pan granulation systems using dolomite powder and lignosulfonate binder. This is a new approach to the study of continuous pan granulation process. Determination of the properties of intermediate product can allow making appropriate changes to the operating parameters to obtain a product with the desired properties without waiting for the formation of the final product.

This approach also makes possible the determination and prediction of the separation factor of the final and intermediate product. The obtained dependencies can be used for the formulation of a mathematical model of underlying granulation process dynamics on arbitrary scales [8]. Such a model enables application of advanced process automation and intensification approaches, which contribute not only to constant production properties but also to sustainable and efficient plant operation.

The manuscript is structured as follows. In the next section, the experimental plant, raw materials used and analytical methods are described along with the experimental plan. The subsequent section contains presentation of the obtained results as well as their discussion and interpretation. In the last section, the results are summarized, and an outlook is given to possible future research.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Raw Materials

The particle material was powdered dolomite. Dolomite was selected because of its wide industrial application, (mainly as construction material and fertilizers) and cheap acquisition costs. The material studied came from the Devonian dolomites quarry for aggregate production, located in the Świętokrzyskie region. The binder solution contains 2.5 - 10 wt% sodium lignosulfonate and 97.5 - 90 wt% of water. Sodium lignosulfonate is water-soluble anionic polyelectrolyte polymers produced from waste compounds from paper manufacturing. Lignosulfonates are characterized by a wide range of applications utilizing their binding, lubricating, dispersing and emulsifying properties.

2.2 Lab-scale pan granulation system

The experiment was realized in a pilot scale pan granulator shown in Figure 2. The pan has an inner diameter of 400 mm, and depth of 100 mm, schematically shown in Figure 3. The particles have been placed in a tank and then using vibratory conveyor transported into the pan. The primary particles were sprayed by a nozzle which was installed in a top-spray configuration at a distance of 350 mm above the pan of the granulator. An external pump and air compressor supplied the feeding of the sprayed binder

solution. The pan is set into rotary motion by a motor (Model AR304, ERWEKA GmbH), with the rotational velocity and pan inclination angle being adjustable in ranges of 2 - 80 rpm and 0 – 70 deg, respectively. The device is designed for continuous operation. It has a hopper for powder material with a vibrating motor for removing overhangs and blockages. The powder material is fed by a vibrating conveyor. The flow rate is adjustable in range 0-250 g/min. The machine is equipped with replaceable binder hoppers. The binder flow, the powder flow and the air flow were controlled with a main control panel (Model CE255, G.U.N.T. Gerätebau GmbH). All components of experimental setup were made of stainless steel and assembled on a metal table.

Fig. 3. Pilot scale pan granulator used for the experiments.

2.3 Analytical methods

The pan samples (intermediate product) and product samples were analyzed offline. PSD of each sample was measured offline with a Mastersizer (Malvern Instruments, Malvern, Worcestershire, United Kingdom), which infers particle size via dynamic light scattering. The output data from the analyzer is PSDs, normalized with respect to the volume of the particle collective for each sample. For granules larger than 2 mm, the sieve analysis method was additionally applied and compiled with the results from Mastersizer. Additionally the D(0.5) and the D(3.2) diameters were determined.

Angle of repose and bulk density were measured used Powder Tester PT-S (Hosokawa Micron B.V. Doetinchem, Netherlands). The bulk density was determined by measuring the mass of bulk solid that occupies a unit volume of a bed, including the volume of all interparticles voids.

The compressive strength was measured using a C9B load cell force tester from HBM (Hottinger Baldwin Messtechnik GmbH, Darmstadt, Germany), with a range up to 200 N. The sensor was coupled to a SPIDER 8 amplifier (HBM) interfacing with a computer. The measurement results were recorded by Catman Easy 2.1 software, which reads the force values indicated by the sensor at a frequency of 50 Hz.

The humidity was determined using a RADWAG MA.R laboratory moisture analyzer (Radom, Poland) in 110°C. Humidity measurements were carried out until a constant weight of the material was obtained at a given temperature.

2.4 Experimental plan and sample collection

In this work, the investigated parameters were powder flow rate, binder flow rate, inclination angle of the pan (IA), rotation speed of the pan (RS), binder concentration in water solution, which result in a total amount of 11 experiments. Each experiment was carried out with the same initial bed mass and the same PSD of primary particles. Dolomite was used as nuclei particles and feeding material. The injected binder solution was a mixture of water and sodium lignosulfonateas binder.

The work started with some preliminary granulation tests and parameter selection for a reference sample. The first experiment was conducted in continuous mode using the parameters shown in Table 1 for the REF sample. Once a steady state was established, the first parameter, i.e., raw material flow rate, was changed and the process was continued until subsequent steady state was attained. The same procedure was followed by changing the operating parameters; the process was not started at the same starting point.

The used binder solution contained 2.5 – 10 wt% sodium lignosulfonate and 90 – 97.5 wt% of water. The feed flow was varied from 40– 80 g/min, and binder flow from 10 - 20 g/min. The IA varied from 20 – 40 deg, the RS from 25 - 35 rpm. The initial bed mass for the experiment was 200 g. The nozzle air flow pressure was 2 bar. An overview of the operation parameters is shown in Table 1 (see nomenclature for further details). It is seen that the parameters are varied “one-at-a-time”, i.e. for investigation of each parameter, two additional experiments were conducted, one with a higher and one with lower value compared to the REF experiment, while the other parameters remained unchanged in the reference configuration. The REF was chosen as a central experiment for the five parameter variations.

Table 1. Experimental plan for the variation of the operation parameters.

Sample number	Sample name	Parameter				
		\dot{M}_{feed} g * min ⁻¹	\dot{M}_b g * min ⁻¹	IA deg	RS rpm	C_b mass%

1	REF	60	15	30	30	5
2	FF1	40	15	30	30	5
3	FF2	80	15	30	30	5
4	BF1	60	10	30	30	5
5	BF2	60	20	30	30	5
6	IA1	60	15	20	30	5
7	IA2	60	15	40	30	5
8	RS1	60	15	30	25	5
9	RS2	60	15	30	35	5
10	CB1	60	15	30	30	2.5
11	CB2	60	15	30	30	10

In each experiment, the pan and product samples were taken systematically. The pan samples were taken manually, directly from the pan. The first parameter measured was the humidity of the product and pan samples. The samples had to be analyzed as soon as possible to avoid moisture loss, which might affect the inaccuracy of the measurements. The granules were then dried at 40°C for 48 hours to obtain the moisture content of 1-2%. The properties of the dried granules were then studied. PSD of the granules was determined at first, followed by the measurements of angle of repose and bulk density. The last parameter determined was the compressive strength of the granules.

3 Results and Discussion

In this section experimental results are discussed. At first, the reference experiment (REF) is discussed in detail. Then, each investigated process operation parameter is discussed individually and results are compared to the reference experiment. For the comparison, the focus is on the following granule properties: PSD, D(0.5) diameter, D(3.2) diameter, angle of repose, aerated bulk density, humidity and mechanical strength.

3.1 Reference experiment

As mentioned above, the reference experiment (REF) was chosen as a central experiment for the seven parameter variations of the two series (see Table 1). It was conducted at temperature of 90 °C with a nuclei feed rate of 60 g/min and an average binder rate of 15 g/min. This reference ratio between binder and nuclei feed ensured appropriate humidity of the primary particles and agglomerates. At the beginning of the experiment, the initial mass of the loaded material was 200 g. The IA was 30 deg, the RS 30 rpm and the used binder solution contained 5 wt% sodium lignosulfonate and 95 wt% of water. The nozzle air flow pressure was 2 bar. The obtained granulation product is shown in Figure 4. The selection of the parameters for the reference sample was based on several preliminary granulation tests.

Fig. 4. Raw material (left) pan (in the middle) and product (right) samples of the granulation.

Figure 5 shows PSD for the product and pan samples used in REF. It can be seen that the product samples have a higher contribution of larger particle sizes, especially for sizes above 20 μm . Under the centrifugal force of the granulator pan, the heavier particles with larger sizes are pushed outside the plate, while the lighter smaller particles still remain inside the pan.

Fig. 5. PSD for product, feed and pan samples of the reference experiment.

For all experimental cases, differences were observed between the product and pan samples indicating the simultaneous segregation and classification in the course of the process.. Considering the nature of running a disc granulation process using rotary motion, this is a situation that was to be expected: larger granules with higher weight under the influence of centrifugal force get out of the granulator faster, whereas smaller granules remain inside the granulator longer. Since the process was carried out continuously, raw material was continuously fed into the granulator plate, which resulted in excess of

un-granulated material in the pan samples in each case. The results obtained may be useful in selecting process conditions suitable for formation of specific grain sizes.

3.2 Effects of process operation parameters on characteristic PSDs

In the first step, the effect of the process parameters on PSD was analyzed for each of the product and pan samples. The results are presented as cumulative size distribution curves with respect to mass (Fig. 6 - 10). A curve for the powder material was included on each graph to facilitate interpretation. The effect of each process parameter on PSD was analyzed for three cases including a reference case with averaged parameters with respect to other samples.

Fig. 6. Influence of the feed flow PSD of product and pan samples of the granulation.

Fig. 7. Influence of the binder flow on PSD of product and pan samples of the granulation.

Each of the changed process parameters affects PSD. The greatest effect was observed by changing the binder flow rate (Fig. 7). The higher the binder flow rate, the larger the granules obtained for both, product and pan samples. The higher the powder flow rate, the smaller the granules obtained. The granule size can therefore be determined by the mass flow ratio of binder liquid to raw material feed. The larger this ratio, the larger the granules. In case of the samples with lower ratios, a higher proportion of un-granulated material is observed, higher for the pan samples than the product samples.

The granule size distribution changes regularly with the change in the binder concentration. The higher binder concentration, the larger the size of granules. The changes are particularly noticeable for the product samples. Increasing the binder concentration can be an alternative to increase in the binder flow rate or decrease in the raw material feed rate.

Fig. 8. Influence of the binder content on PSD of product and pan samples of the granulation.

Regular changes in PSD were also observed when (IA) was changed. The greater IA of the granulator pan, the larger the granules are obtained. The change in IA affects the residence time of the granules in the pan: a larger IA with respect to vertical axis induces a longer residence time. The nuclei formed by a combination of capillary adhesion forces and viscous forces due to the presence of a binder can attach higher amount of powder particles by staying longer in the granulator, resulting in larger granule sizes. Increase in IA also extends the distance that the granules cover inside the granulator, which also enhances attachment of powder particles and results in increase the size..

Fig. 9. Influence of IA on PSD of product and pan samples of the granulation.

Significant changes in PSD were also observed for the samples for which the RS was changed. The higher RS, the larger the granules were obtained. This may be due to the elongation of the distance to be covered by the granules in the pan. Increase in RS causes that the granules under the influence of inertia forces move higher inside the granulator, and thus are in contact with a larger number of raw material particles and can form permanent bonds with them.

Fig. 10. Influence of the RS of the pan on PSD of product samples of pan granulation.

Figs 11-12 illustrate the effect of process conditions on $D(0.5)$ of the products. Significant changes were observed for each of the analyzed parameters. For all cases, $D(0.5)$ of the product samples were larger compared with the pan samples. The most pronounced differences were observed when binder flow rate

was changed. The higher the binder flow rate, the larger the granules obtained. For the sample BF2, the largest differences were observed between the product and pan samples, which indicated that higher binder flow rates have a beneficial effect on D(0.5). The changes in raw material flow rate have the smallest impact D(0.5).

Fig. 11. Influence of the operating parameters on the D(0.5) diameter.

Fig. 12. Influence of the operating parameters on the D(3.2) diameter.

3.3 Effects of the operation parameters on angle of repose

For all cases, larger values of angle of repose were observed for the pan samples than for the product samples. The product samples contain higher amount of granules with a regular shape. When the grains are smooth and rounded, the angle of repose is low. The highest values of angle of repose, and thus the worst flowability, were exhibited by the pan samples of BC1 with the lowest binder concentration and FF2 with the highest raw material flow rate. Both samples contained significant amounts of ungranulated material. The FF1 sample with the lowest raw material flow rate showed the lowest angle of repose value. It can be concluded that the higher amount of granules with larger diameters, the smaller angle of repose, and thus the better flowability of the material. The lower the raw material flow rate, the higher the binder flow rate, the higher AI of the granulator plate, the higher the binder concentration, and the lower the angle of repose value. In case of RS, the changes are the least significant for investigated parameter variations.

Fig. 13. Influence of the operating parameters on angle of repose.

3.4 Effects of the process operation parameters on bulk density

As in case of angle of repose, higher bulk density values were observed for the pan samples than for the product, as pan samples contained more ungranulated raw material. The samples with the lowest ratio of binder flow rate to raw material flow rate, i.e., FF2 and BF1, had the highest bulk density. They contained the most powder material with a small size. Small raw material particles can fill free space between the granules, and thus increase bulk density and impair flowability of the material. The higher value of bulk density, the higher the raw material flow rate, the lower the binder flow rate, the smaller

AI of the granulator plate and the lower the binder concentration. As in case of angle of repose, changes in RS are the least significant for the investigated samples.

Fig. 14. Influence of the operating parameters on bulk density.

3.5 Effects of the operation parameters on compressive strength

The compressive strength varied significantly depending on the operating parameters. A correlation between particle size and compressive strength was observed. Larger granules had higher compressive strength. This trend was observed for all cases, higher compressive strength was observed for the product samples than for the pan samples. The BC2 sample with the highest binder concentration had the highest compressive strength. In this case, the viscous forces from the binder were so high that the compressive strength is over 110 N. Also, the samples with higher binder to raw material flow ratio (FF1, BF2) are characterized by higher compressive strength. Changes in AI of the granulator plate and the RS do not significantly affect the compressive strength. Samples FF2 and BF1 show the lowest strength values, unacceptable for use as granular fertilizer.

Fig. 15. Influence of the operating parameters on compressive strength.

3.6 Effects of process operation parameters on humidity

The results obtained reveal an increase $D(0.5)$ with increasing moisture content. The samples with the highest moisture content also show the highest value of compressive strength. Samples with the highest moisture content have a lower bulk density value, which seems to be the opposite to the expected result. However, it should be taken into account that the bulk density value is also affected by the presence of a large amount of un-granulated raw material, and in the case of samples with a high moisture content a predominance of granules with the size larger than the powdered raw material is observed. The higher the moisture content, the lower angle of repose; that conclusion may also contradict the general trend of increasing the value of angle of repose with increasing moisture content, and thus the cohesion of the powder materials.

An increase in moisture content results in more durable granules with regular shapes. The process of granule growth prevails over granule disintegration. The obtained granules are characterized by a regular spherical shape, which facilitated the movement of granules in relation to each other and thus reduced the value of angle of repose (improves flowability). The higher the ratio of binder flow rate to raw material, the higher IA of the granulator (higher residence time in the granulator), the higher the RS and the higher the binder concentration, the higher the material moisture content. A higher moisture content was observed for the pan samples, which can be related to the higher residence time of the particles in the granulator. Another reason may be the fact that in the pan smaller and wetter particles have a higher density and segregate to the bottom of the pan. Those particles are not observed in such quantities in the product.

Fig. 16. Influence of the operating parameters on the humidity.

4 Conclusion and Outlook

The aim of the study was investigation of the influence of different operating parameters on the process behavior and properties of product quality in pan granulation. The effects of process parameters on granule size distribution, average granule size, angle of repose, bulk density, compressive strength, and humidity were investigated. A significant effect of process parameters on the measured properties was observed.

The settings of the process parameters have a clear effect on particle size distribution and the average diameter of the granules obtained. The results obtained indicate an increase in the average particle size with increasing binder flow rate to feed rate ratio, increasing binder concentration and inclination angle of the pan.

Compressive strength varied significantly depending on the operating parameters. A relationship between particle size and compressive strength was observed. Larger granules were characterized by higher compressive strength. To produce large particles with smaller compressive strength, smaller amounts of binder liquid should be used.

For all cases, larger values of angle of repose were observed for the pan samples than for product samples. The product samples contain higher amount of larger granules with a regular shape. When the granules are smooth and rounded, the angle of repose is low. The highest values of angle of repose, and thus the worst flowability, were exhibited by the pan samples with the lowest binder concentration and with the highest raw material flow rate. As in case of angle of repose, higher bulk density values were

observed for the pan samples than for the product samples, since the pan samples contained higher amount of un-granulated raw material. The samples with the lowest ratio of binder flow rate to raw material flow rate had the highest bulk density.

To produce granules with larger sizes, it is recommended to increase the ratio of binder flow rate to raw material rate, increase the inclination angle, increase the rotation speed of the pan and increase the binder concentration. To produce granule with higher flowability, it is recommended to increase the ratio of binder flow rate to raw material, increase the inclination angle, increase the rotation speed of the pan and increase the binder concentration. To obtain higher mechanical strength of the granules, increase in the binder flow rate ratio to the raw material, or increase in the binder concentration is recommended. The inclination angle and rotation speed of the pan do not cause significant changes in mechanical strength of the granules. To obtain granules with a higher moisture content, it is recommended to increase the binder flow rate relative to the raw material, increase the binder concentration or inclination angle and rotation speed.

Additional experiments will be conducted in the future to investigate the effects of simultaneous variation of a few operation parameters. Such research will further improve the understanding of the process and allow identification of favorable process regimes. The properties of the granules obtained depend on the operating parameters that affect the residence time of the granules in the granulator. Therefore, future work should focus on the determination of the residence time distribution of granules in the granulator and its influence on the properties of pan granulation products. Furthermore, detailed investigation of the simultaneous segregation and separation effects has to be conducted. The presented results will also form a sound basis for mathematical modeling of the process dynamics and temporal evolution of the product granule properties, e.g. using population balance equations [40,41]. Those can facilitate the application of sophisticated process intensification and automatic control approaches to ensure sustainable plant operation and constant product quality and throughput for continuous operation mode in face of unforeseen disturbances.

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Nomenclature

d diameter μm

\dot{M}	mass flow rate	$\text{g}^* \text{min}^{-1}$
t	time	s
T	temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
C	mass binder content	%

Greek letters

ρ	density	$\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$
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Subscripts

aggl	agglomerate
b	binder
pan	pan sample
feed	nuclei feed
in	inlet
out	outlet
pp	primary particles
pro	product
sep	separation

Abbreviations

AOR	angle of repose	[deg]
BC	binder mass content	[%]
BF	binder mass flow	[g/min]
FF	feed mass flow	[g/min]
IA	inclination angle of the pan	[deg]
PSD	particle size distribution	
REF	reference experiment	
RS	Rotation speed of the pan	[rpm]
SMD	Sauter mean diameter	[μm]

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